

ELIMINATION OF DEFICIENCIES IN WRITTEN SPEECH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article discusses how to eliminate the shortcomings of students' written speech. And information is provided about the correct and effective use of the methods and methods used in improving their literacy.

Keywords: speech, written speech, oral speech, sounds, speech development, meaningfulness of speech, logic of speech, independent thinking.

УСТРАНЕНИЕ НЕДОСТАТКОВ ПИСЬМЕННОЙ РЕЧИ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются способы устранения недостатков письменной речи учащихся. И предоставляется информация о правильном и эффективном использовании методов и приемов, применяемых при повышении их грамотности.

Ключевые слова: речь, письменная речь, устная речь, звуки, развитие речи, осмысленность речи, логика речи, самостоятельное мышление.

INTRODUCTION

Until now, it is known that a number of scientific works, candidate dissertations, manuals and articles have been created that provide practical help in education and upbringing of young people and simplify the process of imparting knowledge. However, the scientific works aimed at making students learn independently and work independently, and the scientific works on the shortcomings of their written speech remain one of the current topics.

By teaching students to work independently, developing their written speech, it encourages them to work independently, to think independently, to conduct independent experiments, to draw independent conclusions, and to develop students' thinking skills, expand their thinking, and increase their scientific competence. That is why it is very important to teach elementary school students to work independently and write well.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Speech is a means of expressing thoughts, expressed in oral and written form. Thinking takes place with the help of it, thanks to which people communicate with each other. If oral speech reaches the listener through pauses, emphasis, intonation and sounds, written speech is a combination of letters and words based on a certain law, punctuation marks, various separations, grammatically clear sentences and reaches through pronunciation of sounds .

Another difference between spoken speech and written speech is that we hear spoken speech, see and read written speech. Written speech is a complex process that requires a lot of work. In terms of syntax, written speech is the most complete and perfect speech. This speech is the best way to express our free will. Written speech develops on the basis of oral speech.

Oral speech develops by interacting with people in life, imitating them, and does not require special reading and learning from the child. Written speech is a speech intended for

visual perception of sounds, words, sentences with the help of letters and symbols, and writing by hand.

Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on a language tool (word, phrase, sentence). Speech performs the function of communication and communication, expressing one's thoughts with emotions and influencing others. A well-developed speech serves as one of the important means of human activity in society. For the student, speech is a tool for successful education at school.

RESULTS

What is speech development? If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical acquisition of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, the development of speech means the use of methods and techniques that help students to actively master the pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure and connected speech. That is why the grammar and spelling program includes parts such as sounds and letters, words, sentences, and connected speech. The sections of the mother tongue program are called: "Literacy and Speech Development", "Reading and Speech Development", "Grammar, Spelling and Speech Development". .

For speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech, it is necessary to comply with several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for a person's speech to emerge. The methodical requirement of developing students' speech is to create a situation in which the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally or in writing.
2. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be. Therefore, the second condition for the development of students' speech is to take care of the material of speech exercises, to make the child's speech meaningful.
3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using words, phrases, sentences, speech information that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools. It is necessary to give children language samples and create good speech conditions for them. As a result of hearing speech and using it in their own experience, children develop a conscious "language perception" on which the educational methodology is based.
4. According to the methods of expression, speech is oral and written. Spoken speech differs from written speech as follows: spoken speech is sound speech, and written speech is graphic speech. In oral speech, the sense of hearing, and in written speech, the sense of sight and motor movement (hand movements) take the main place. Both oral speech and written speech serve as a means of communication between people, but oral speech occurs in specific life conditions, directly in the process of communication; in written speech, it is used directly, separated from specific circumstances, and without the participation of a person.
5. Oral speech is often in the form of a dialogue, and written speech is in the form of a monologue. Written speech requires logical consistency, without omitting certain language forms, and without excessive repetition, so written speech is considered more complex and abstract.

A number of clearly defined requirements are observed in the development of students' speech:

Let the students' speech be meaningful. A story or an essay will be meaningful only if it is built on the basis of well-known facts for students, their observations, life experiences, information received from books, pictures, radio broadcasts and TV shows. If children are allowed to talk about things they don't know, events they haven't seen, without sufficient preparation, the speech will be poor and meaningless.

DISCUSSION

The method of speech development requires careful preparation of the material for the story, essay, i.e. collecting the material, discussing it, filling it, separating its main content, placing it in the necessary consistency. Of course, the age characteristics and interests of students are also taken into account.

1. Let there be logic in the speech. It is required that students' speech should be logically correct, the idea should be presented coherently and reasonably, not to leave out the main points and not to allow unnecessary repetition and redundancy that does not apply to the topic. The logicity of the speech is determined by good knowledge of things, events, and the logical error is caused by not knowing the content of the material and choosing the topic without thinking. These two requirements relate to the content and construction of the speech. There are also requirements for the formation of speech in terms of language.
2. Let the speech be clear. The student should learn to express facts, observations, and impressions with special images, using the best language tools (words, phrases, sentences) in accordance with the truth.
3. Let the speech be rich in language tools. In order to clearly express the content, the student's speech should be rich in language tools, it is necessary to have the ability to use the necessary synonyms and various structured sentences to choose the most suitable for the content in any situation. Of course, it is impossible to make high demands on the language skills of elementary school students, but the teacher should always keep in mind to increase their vocabulary in educational work.
4. Let the speech be understandable. Oral speech should be understandable to the listener, and written speech should be understandable to the reader. If a speaker or writer makes his speech taking into account the possibility and interest of the listener or reader, everyone will understand it equally and without difficulty.
5. Let the speech be expressive. If the speech is expressive, that is, lively, beautiful, persuasive, affects the listener through intonation, both oral and written speech convey to the listener and reader the general spirit of the story, arguments, selected words, their Affects emotionality using structured sentences and phrases. The intelligibility and expressiveness of the speech requires that it be free from any dialect and redundant words.
6. Let the speech be correct. It is of particular importance for the school that the speech conforms to the norms of the literary language. Written speech must be structured correctly in terms of grammar, spelling and punctuation, and oral speech in terms of orthography. The choice of words and the logic of speech are very important for the speech to be correct.

CONCLUSIONS

The requirements listed above are interrelated and are comprehensively implemented in the system of school work.

Speech is not only a means of expressing an idea, but also a tool for its formation. Thought performs the main psychological function of speech, and the condition for its growth is thought enrichment. It is possible to successfully develop speech only on the basis of mastering the system of mental activity. Therefore, great importance is attached to the preparation, improvement of the material, the selection, placement and logical operations of the material in the development of students' speech.

Thought grows successfully only if it is verbally formed and expressed with the help of language material. The concept is expressed by words or word combinations, therefore, the concept becomes an important communication material in the word, which is a language tool. Only if a person knows the word (combination of words) that expresses a concept, based on this concept, he will have the opportunity to think in external speech.

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